

Investigating the Interplay Between Cervical Spine Sagittal Balance and Lower Back Pain

Using Computational Biomechanics and Biomedical Imaging

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Background

- Understanding cervical sagittal balance has emerged as a crucial diagnostic criterion due to the relationship between disability, horizontalization of the gaze¹, and multiple neuropathologies.
- Biomechanically, the cervical spine behavior it is important to recognize that the forward head posture moves the center of the body mass forward the C1-C2 comprising approximately 40% of the total cervical flexion and 60% of the total cervical rotation²
- The joints and mechanical components of the upper cervical spine are complex and difficult to understand conventionally,³

Finite element is used to understand it more deeply.

- We aim to develop a morphologically simplified finite element model of the C1-C5 segment to examine the stresses and strains experienced by the cervical spine under multi-modal loading, to simulate the influence of the upper cervical region on the other cervical vertebrae spanning from C1 to C5.

Methods

- Computational modeling has been used to simulate the influence of the upper cervical spine with respect to the other cervical vertebrae from C1 to C5. This was achieved by developing a morphologically simplified finite element model of the C1-C5 spine in FEBio Studio 2.1.2 (www.febio.org).

Conclusion

- Emulating superior and anterior compression, the effective strain trend was shown in the postero-superior and the deformation in C1-C2-C3 and antero-inferior for C4-C5.
- In addition, it can be predicted how the intervertebral discs deform in response to the anterior displacement of the upper segment. In this case, it is representing the upper cervical in the forward head posture position.

Finite Element

- The cervical spine geometry was discretized using a 8-node hexahedral mesh. Contact interaction properties were assigned using Facet-to-Facet parameters to the superior and inferior endplate emulating the linking between endplate and intervertebral disc (IVD) surfaces. Four ligaments were modelled representing Posterior Longitudinal Ligaments and Four ligaments representing Anterior Longitudinal Ligaments.

Boundary conditions

In order to emulate a simple cervical spine model, a fixed boundary condition was applied to the bottom vertebrae (C5). **Figure 1** A prescribed displacement of 0.7 mm in the negative Z-direction was applied to C1 to simulate compression of the spine. A second simulation was performed simulating a 2 mm lateral displacement of C1.

Results

- In the top displacement (Compression) the stress distributed throughout the spine is slightly reflected in the vertebral bodies with but more intensely in the ligamentous insertions. Whereas strain is more pronounced in the IVDs, especially in the outer circumference. The strain is observed attenuated in the IVDs of C1-C2 and C4-C5 and a minuscule deformation in the IVDs C2-C3 and C3-C4.
- Prescribing both the stress is pronounced in the posterior-inferior ligamentous insertion of C1, the complete posterior block of C2 and the posterior-superior ligamentous insertion of C3. In the lower part, the postero-inferior ligamentous insertion of C3 is detailed, the complete anterior block of C4 and a moderate part in anterior C5.

Figure 2

References

- 1- Hasegawa, et al. 2017. Standing sagittal alignment of the whole axial skeleton with reference to the gravity line in humans. *Journal of Anatomy*, 230, 619-630.
- 2- Frankel, M. N. A. V. 2021. *Basic Biomechanics of the Musculoskeletal System*, Wilters Kluwer
- 3- Maas, S. A., et al. 2012. FEBio: finite elements for biomechanics. *J Biomech Eng*, 134, 011005.

Figure 1 Boundary condition and Prescribed displacement of the finite element model of the C1-C5 sagittal cervical spine.

Figure 2 Effective strain **a** displacement (Horn et al.), **b** displacement (y-), **c** displacement (z-y) of the finite element model of the C1-C5 sagittal cervical spine.